

AQUARIUS Technical Training **Hub – Training Material** **repository**

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About this document

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<input type="checkbox"/>	CO: Confidential, only for members of the consortium (including the Commission)

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1. Executive Summary

This document outlines the development and current status of the AQUARIUS Technical Training Hub and Materials Repository. The hub includes a variety of training materials produced by the AQUARIUS project as well as other relevant training resources developed across other European Funded projects and EU RI networks addressing 'Healthy Oceans and Waters'. The materials have been collated in the AQUARIUS training hub to provide a single source for all resources. Resources include online e-learning digital resources, tools, technical specifications, presentations and webinars. [The Training Hub](#) will continue to be updated with the addition of new resources as they are developed and made available throughout the project, including any relevant outputs from the AQUARIUS [Training Opportunities](#).

The RI Technical Training Materials Repository aims to provide customized information and support for the effective use of integrated research infrastructures and for the management of consistent, high quality data management and open science practices across all user projects, from the integration of sophisticated data infrastructures to the provision of practical user support.

2. Technical Training Hub

Work package 5 (RI Technical Training) aims to provide customized and highly efficient training and scientific & technical support to users of the AQUARIUS research infrastructures. In addition, participants are invited to take part in specific training on data management and data governance and will be introduced to open-science practices.

The AQUARIUS Training Hub is a repository for training materials that provide information on and access to customized training material developed within the AQUARIUS project and by project partners. The hub also provides access to relevant materials developed in other European projects and EU research infrastructure networks.

The Training Hub and the material repository are available on the AQUARIUS project website ([link](#)).

It is divided into four subfolders:

- Research Infrastructures Technical Training Resources
- AQUARIUS Webinars
- Data Management and Analytics
- Healthy Ocean and Waters

TRAINING HUB

This AQUARIUS Training Hub is a training material repository providing information on and access to tailored training material developed in the AQUARIUS project. The hub also provides access to relevant materials developed across other European projects and EU Research Infrastructure networks.

Research Infrastructures
Technical Training Resources

AQUARIUS Webinars

Data Management & Analytics

Healthy Ocean & Waters

2.1. Research Infrastructures Technical Training Resources

The following [link](#) provides further information and materials from the AQUARIUS research infrastructure providers.

**RESEARCH
INFRASTRUCTURES
TECHNICAL TRAINING
RESOURCES**

At the links below you can find additional information and material from the AQUARIUS research infrastructure providers.

- ▶ [Research infrastructures' training material](#)

- ▶ [Research infrastructure posters](#)

- ▶ [Eurofleets](#)

2.1.1. Research Infrastructures Training Material

In this section, AQUARIUS project partners have provided additional material on their infrastructures to help users select the most suitable infrastructures for their scientific project and to properly exploit the infrastructure. In total, 31 information materials on research infrastructures are available, containing information on standard operating procedures (SOPs) for CTD and Seabed mapping, training material to ensure appropriate and efficient use of the RI, webinars and tutorials with practical training material.

2.1.2. Research Infrastructures posters

Research Infrastructure (RI) operators were asked to create posters showcasing the scientific and technical capabilities of their infrastructures for the first AQUARIUS brokerage event, held during the 2024 ICES Annual Science Conference. These posters were later published on the AQUARIUS Training Hub to help Call applicants and users make informed decisions when writing their Transnational Access (TA) applications. Currently, 43 posters are available to users, and can be viewed at the following [link](#) in the Research Infrastructure Technical Training Resources.

2.1.3. Eurofleets Ocean Classroom

An online [Ocean Classroom](#) was developed during the EU Horizon 2020 funded Eurofleets+ project which contains many useful educational resources relating to marine research infrastructures, our oceans and marine science. Resources include videos, presentations, posters, infographics and activity sheets. The classroom contains online resources that are suitable for children, members of the public, marine scientists and research infrastructure operators. These resources are shared via the AQUARIUS Training Hub.

2.2. Webinars

There have been a series of information webinars held throughout the AQUARIUS project. So far, 4 webinars have taken place, the recordings have been shared in the Training Hub and can be found at the following [link](#).

The screenshot shows a webpage titled "WEBINARS" with a decorative header image of a coastal landscape. Below the title, a text block states: "AQUARIUS will organise a variety of Webinars throughout the course of the project. You can find all the Webinar recordings below." There are four webinar cards arranged in a 2x2 grid:

- Webinar 1:** "Transnational Access to Research Infrastructure Funding Call – How to Apply". The card features a YouTube video thumbnail with the title "AQUARIUS Webinar: Transnational Access to Research Infrastructure Funding Call – How to Apply".
- Webinar 2:** "AQUARIUS Training – Learn to use the call application platform". The card features a YouTube video thumbnail with the title "AQUARIUS Training - Learn to use the call application platform".
- Webinar 3:** "FAIR Data Principles". The card features a YouTube video thumbnail with the title "AQUARIUS webinar - FAIR Data Principles". Below the card, there is a link for "Download Slides".
- Webinar 4:** "Data Management". The card features a YouTube video thumbnail with the title "AQUARIUS - Data Management Webinar". Below the card, there is a link for "Download Slides".

2.2.1. Webinar 1

[Transnational Access to Research Infrastructure Funding Call – How to Apply.](#)
See Deliverable 5.2 - Training on use of AQUARIUS Access Platform.

2.2.2. Webinar 2

[AQUARIUS Training – Learn to use the call application platform](#)

See Deliverable 5.2 - Training on use of AQUARIUS Access Platform.

2.2.3. Webinar 3 and 4

These training webinars informed and trained researchers on European marine data infrastructures, FAIR (Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, Reusable) standards, services and tools that they can use to process, document and input their newly collected data and the resulting data products. The training programme consisted of a series of presentations and practical exercises and were delivered by a number of experts in a series of online workshops. The experts are geographically distributed across the European marine regions and will also be active in the actual implementation of the data management concept. The webinar(s) were recorded and are available on the AQUARIUS Training Hub.

["Webinar 3 - FAIR Data Principles – Literature and related web resources review"](#) was shared in May 2025.

In webinar 3, Sissy Iona (HCMR) presented the FAIR Principles, what FAIR Data consists of, FAIR extensions and the AQUARIUS approach to addressing the FAIR principles.

A screenshot of a presentation slide. The slide has a white background with a thin blue border. In the top right corner, there is a small AQUARIUS logo. The main content is a bulleted list under the heading "Scope of presentation". The list items are: "What FAIR Principles are", "What FAIR Data is", "FAIR extensions", and "AQUARIUS approach in addressing FAIR". There is a vertical blue line on the right side of the slide, and a small speaker icon with the number "2" is in the bottom right corner.

Scope of presentation
• What FAIR Principles are
• What FAIR Data is
• FAIR extensions
• AQUARIUS approach in addressing FAIR

Table 1: Agenda of the Webinar 3 'FAIR Data Principles'

['Webinar 4 - FAIR Data Management'](#) was held on 11th June 2025, 14:00-15:30 CET. The speakers and the topics of the webinar were introduced by Sissy Iona (HCMR), as moderator of the webinar.

Agenda

Presentation	Presenter	Time	Duration	Organization
Welcome & Introduction to the AQUARIUS Data Management Approach	Sissy Iona	14.00 CEST	15 minutes	Hellenic Centre for Marine Research (HCMR)
EMODnet contribution to EDITO	Conor Delaney	14.15 CEST	10 minutes	EMODnet
SeaDataNet Pan-European infrastructure for ocean & marine data management	Sissy Iona	14.25 CEST	15 minutes	Hellenic Centre for Marine Research (HCMR)
EMODnet Biology/EurOBIS marine biodiversity data management	Ruben Perez	14.40 CEST	10 minutes	Flanders Marine Institute (VLIZ)
Data Summary Log APP & EMODnet Data Ingestion service	Dick Schaap	14.50 CEST	20 minutes	MARIS
Q/A Session	All	15.10 CEST	15 minutes	N/A
Follow up Actions	Sissy Iona	15.25 CEST	5 minutes	Hellenic Centre for Marine Research (HCMR)

Table 2: Agenda for Webinar 4 'Fair Data Management'

28 participants, each of whom are involved in one of the successful TA proposals from Call 1, registered and took part in the training webinar 'Data Management'. Feedback from the participants was very positive. The webinar has been recorded and is available in the AQUARIUS Training Hub and on YouTube, where it has been viewed > 41 times.

2.3. Data Management and Analytics

DATA MANAGEMENT & ANALYTICS

Data collection is a costly and time-consuming business. Data collected for one purpose can be used for another purpose. Making data available in a way that people can find it and use it maximises the benefit that can be derived from data collected with public funds. This is the principle of open data at the heart of AQUARIUS.

How will we implement an open data strategy in AQUARIUS?

All scientific teams using the research infrastructures will commit to adopting a common AQUARIUS approach for managing and publishing the data they collect, as well as any resulting data products and knowledge (in the form of scientific papers, for example). This approach is laid out in the [AQUARIUS Data Management Plan](#).

The scientific teams funded through the AQUARIUS transnational access programme will collect many new and diverse types of data as they use and combine multiple different observation infrastructures. AQUARIUS is committed to making these data open and **FAIR (Findable, Accessible, Interoperable and Reusable)** to maximise their re-use by other actors – be they research scientists, companies carrying out environmental impact assessments, public monitoring bodies, or civil society organisations.

What training will be made available in data management and analytics?

AQUARIUS will also introduce and educate the scientific teams in the opportunities of Open Science, as promoted and encouraged by the European Open Science Cloud (EOSC). The scientists will be trained in FAIR data management and introduced to the [Blue-Cloud Virtual Research Environment \(VRE\)](#) and [EDITO](#) (the public infrastructure for the European Digital Twin of the Ocean) for further analyses and processing of AQUARIUS data into new FAIR data products and knowledge.

[View the FAIR DATA Principles Webinar - Literature and related web resources review](#)

[Download the FAIR Data Principles Slides - Literature and related web resources review](#)

This section of the Training Hub is dedicated to training materials related to Data Management and Analytics. All scientific teams using AQUARIUS RIs commit to adopting a common AQUARIUS approach to the management and publication of the data they collect and any resulting data products and findings (e.g. in the form of scientific papers). This approach is set out in the [AQUARIUS Data Management Plan](#), and is discussed in Webinars 3 & 4.

AQUARIUS will introduce and educate the scientific teams in the opportunities of Open Science, as promoted and encouraged by the European Open Science Cloud (EOSC). All funded scientists will be trained in FAIR data management and introduced to the [Blue-Cloud Virtual Research Environment \(VRE\)](#) and [EDITO](#) (the public infrastructure for the European Digital Twin of the Ocean) for further analyses and processing of AQUARIUS data

into new FAIR data products and knowledge. All future materials arising from this specific training will be shared in the AQUARIUS Training Hub Data Management and Analytics section.

2.4. Healthy Ocean & Water

The aim of the AQUARIUS transnational access program is to support research and innovation activities that address the challenges and explore opportunities for the long-term sustainability of our marine and freshwater ecosystems in order to achieve the objectives of the EU Mission: Restore our Ocean and Waters by 2030" and the European Green Deal.

TA users can find out more about the EU Mission Restore our Ocean and Waters by 2030 by following the links below within the Training Hub:

- [Mission Implementation Plan](#)
- [Restore our Ocean and Waters: A CORDIS synergy info pack](#)

3. State of the Art and Future Development

The following materials are currently available in the AQUARIUS Training Hub:

- 31 information materials on research infrastructures, containing information on standard operating procedures for CTD and seabed mapping, guidance and case studies;
- 43 posters on the scientific and technical capabilities of AQUARIUS RIs,
- 2 webinars to support users in the TA call procedures,
- 2 webinars to inform and educate users on the Data Management Plan and Fair Data, and a document on the AQUARIUS Data Management Plan,
- Information on initiatives and projects to "Restore our oceans and waters by 2030"

The AQUARIUS Training Hub is a dynamic repository into which additional information material will be inserted throughout the AQUARIUS project as they are developed and/or become available.